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THE VOICE OF CULTURAL DIPLOMACY: THE HEYDAR ALIYEV FOUNDATION AND THE GLOBAL MISSION OF AZERBAIJANI LITERATURE AND MUSIC

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Abstract

This article examines the role of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, established in 2004, in the development, international promotion, and cultural diplomacy of Azerbaijani literature and music. The study analyzes the foundation's cooperation with UNESCO and other international organizations, translation and promotion projects of classical and contemporary literature, the worldwide presentation of the heritage of such great figures as Nizami and Mahsati Ganjavi, as well as the importance of musical events such as the "Mugham Alemi" festivals and the anniversaries of Bulbul and Shostakovich. The article shows that the Heydar Aliyev Foundation is not just a charitable organization, but an institutional cultural powerhouse that systematically promotes and preserves Azerbaijani culture. Under the leadership of Mehriban Aliyeva, the foundation has introduced Azerbaijan on the international stage with its projects combining literature and music, and has both strengthened national identity and promoted the ideals of mutual understanding and peace between peoples through cultural diplomacy.

Keywords: Azerbaijani culture, Heydar Aliyev Foundation, Cultural diplomacy, Musical iris, UNESCO cooperation.

Introduction: The Heydar Aliyev Foundation is one of the important public institutions that played a leading role in the formation of cultural and social life in Azerbaijan during the period of independence. The Foundation's activities are not limited to its charitable mission, but also aim to provide systematic support to the development of national culture, education and health, and to protect the social well-being and spiritual integrity of the Azerbaijani people. By implementing various humanitarian, scientific and cultural projects within the country, the organization has become an important tool in the formation of the modern face of Azerbaijan and strengthening its international image [7, pp. 184–190].

The Foundation's multifaceted activities also serve to deepen cultural, social and economic relations between Azerbaijan and Turkey, and to strengthen the environment of mutual understanding and cooperation [16, pp. 184–195]. The programs implemented in this direction are of strategic importance not only for the relations between the two countries, but also for the integration processes of the Turkic world as a whole [15, p. 22].

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation has made special contributions to the international promotion of Azerbaijani culture through its projects in literature, music, art and other fields. The Foundation's initiative has not only focused on collecting and promoting examples of oral and written literature, but also on preserving classical Azerbaijani music and folk art in a modern cultural environment [2, p. 138; 3, p. 20].

Education and health projects have a special place among the humanitarian activities of the organization. With the financial support of the foundation, the establishment of the Thalassaemia Center in Baku, the construction and rehabilitation of a number of schools, kindergartens and hospitals, as well as steps taken to expand educational opportunities for young people, have

become an integral part of the social development strategy of Azerbaijan [4, pp. 110–113; 14, pp. 5–9].

In this regard, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation acts as a carrier of a national mission aimed not only at preserving cultural heritage, but also at passing it on to future generations. It acts as one of the main symbolic institutions in the protection of the national identity, spiritual values, and historical memory of the Azerbaijani people [8, p. 186; 9, p. 247].

- Haydar Aliyev Foundation and its importance

The Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev Foundation was established on May 10, 2004 and has become one of the main leading institutions in the social, cultural and humanitarian development of the country. The purpose of the foundation's establishment was to continue the political and spiritual legacy of the national leader Heydar Aliyev, to bring his philosophy of "service to the people" to life in real projects. This mission stems from the desire to strengthen national solidarity at both the ideological and practical levels and to systematically promote the idea of "Azerbaijanism" in modern conditions [7, pp. 184–185].

The motivation for the foundation's establishment has deep socio-political roots. In the political legacy of Heydar Aliyev, the preservation of national identity, the development of culture and education were considered one of the main priorities of state policy. From this point of view, the establishment of the foundation named after him can be considered as a continuation of these ideas and their institutionalization [7, pp. 188–190; 14, p. 2]. The focus of the foundation's activities is on promoting an atmosphere of friendship, cooperation and mutual understanding both within the country and internationally.

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation has carried out wide-ranging activities in areas such as the protection of cultural heritage, support for projects in the fields of education and healthcare, and the implementation of

social welfare programs [17]. One of the main tasks of the organization is to pay special attention to the welfare and development of children, who are considered the future of Azerbaijan, and to raise them as creative citizens shaped by national values [18]. To this end, the foundation attaches importance to programs aimed at the education and upbringing of the younger generation, and considers the transfer of Heydar Aliyev's spiritual heritage to future generations a strategic priority [19].

Since its inception, the Foundation has invested in education and healthcare infrastructure, and has achieved significant achievements in the areas of school rehabilitation, hospital modernization, and scholarship programs [4, pp. 110–113]. For example, the establishment of the Thalassemia Center in Baku and the reconstruction of kindergartens and boarding schools in many regions have made concrete contributions to supporting the state's social policy [14, pp. 5–9].

In the field of culture, the foundation has paid great attention to the international promotion of Azerbaijani literature, music and art. Concerts, exhibitions and folklore events organized by the Heydar Aliyev Foundation have become an important means of presenting the national heritage to the world [2, p. 138; 3, p. 21]. At the same time, architectural monuments such as the Heydar Aliyev Cultural Center built in Baku have become modern cultural symbols of the country and have ensured the promotion of Azerbaijani culture on a global level [8, p. 186; 9, p. 247].

The Foundation's cultural projects have also played an important role in strengthening national self-awareness and feelings of patriotism. Heydar Aliyev has repeatedly emphasized that "the strength of the people lies in its cultural heritage", and the Foundation's activities are a practical confirmation of this principle [8, p. 188]. On his initiative, various grant and competition programs were implemented to support the creativity of artists, writers and musicians [20].

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation of Azerbaijan plays an active role not only in domestic projects, but also in international cooperation. The Foundation has implemented humanitarian projects in cooperation with UNESCO, ISESCO and other international organizations, organized exhibitions and presentations promoting Azerbaijani culture in various countries [6, p. 73; 12, p. 4]. This activity has served to strengthen the "soft power" mechanism of Azerbaijani diplomacy and increase the country's international prestige [16, p. 190–192].

In general, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation acts as an institution of strategic importance in the development of Azerbaijani society. Its activities provide a synthesis of state policy and civil society initiatives, maintaining a balance between social welfare, cultural heritage and national identity. In this regard, the history and significance of the foundation can be assessed not only from the aspect of charity, but also as an institutional embodiment of the modern model of the ideology of Azerbaijanianess [7, p. 189; 15, p. 24].

- **Heydar Aliyev Foundation and Azerbaijani Literature**

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation is one of the leading cultural institutions that systematically supports the development of Azerbaijani culture and literature, and carries the mission of preserving the country's spiritual values and passing them on to future generations. Since its inception, the Foundation has implemented special projects aimed at the development of literature and art, and has put forward numerous initiatives to identify talents in this field and support their creative potential [21].

One of the most important initiatives implemented by the Foundation is the recognition of the work of writers and poets who have contributed to literature through prestigious awards such as the "Heydar Aliyev Award". This initiative does not stop at celebrating literary achievements, but also encourages a culture of competition, professionalism and artistic excellence in the creative environment [3, pp. 19–22]. At the same time, the Foundation's support for the legal protection of Azerbaijani folklore and the revival of traditional literary styles confirms its consistent policy towards the preservation of national and cultural identity [3, pp. 20–24].

As a result of these activities, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation has become an important tool in the recognition of Azerbaijani literature both nationally and internationally. The Foundation makes a continuous contribution to the revitalization of the literary environment, the support of young writers, and the promotion of national literature worldwide [7, pp. 185–188]. Azerbaijani literature has rich traditions that reflect the historical experience, aesthetic sense, and spiritual values of the people. From ancient epics and folk tales to modern novels and poetry, this literature has skillfully combined the diverse cultural influences and human emotions of the people [1, pp. 268–271].

Classics such as Nizami Ganjavi, Fuzuli, and Mirza Fatali Akhundzadeh, who are the main pillars of the literary tradition, are considered symbolic figures representing Azerbaijani literature in both the Eastern and Western worlds. Their works are poetic embodiments of human values, reflecting the themes of humanity, love, justice, and wisdom, and have stood the test of time and continue to have a profound impact on readers today [1, pp. 272–275]. The legacy of these classics is evidence of the contributions of Azerbaijani literature not only to national but also to the literary thought of the Turkic and Islamic worlds.

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation has been actively involved in the protection and promotion of this heritage, and has implemented a number of important projects, particularly under the leadership of the First Lady of Azerbaijan, President of the Foundation, Mehriban Aliyeva [17]. The Foundation has initiated events to restore historical manuscripts, publish classical literature, and promote the work of contemporary writers and poets [8, p. 189; 9, p. 247]. The Foundation has also promoted Azerbaijani literature on international platforms through literary festivals, competitions, and conferences, and has provided financial and moral support to young writers and translators [20].

Within the framework of these activities, the foundation has supported the publication and dissemination

of Azerbaijani literature at the international level by establishing cooperation with both local and foreign publishing houses [31]. This systematization of literary projects has given impetus to the development of the creative environment in the country and created conditions for literature to play a more active role in the life of society [4, p. 115].

The official visit of the representatives of the Azerbaijan Writers' Union and the Azerbaijan University of Economics (UNEC) to the Heydar Aliyev Foundation on December 9, 2005, also had symbolic significance in this regard. The purpose of the visit was to commemorate the memory of the national leader and express respect for his role in the cultural and spiritual development of the country [9, pp. 244–246]. During the visit, the participants were presented with materials stored in the foundation's archives – documents, photographs and books reflecting Heydar Aliyev's childhood and youth, various stages of his statehood activities and an entire period of Azerbaijani history [7, p. 190].

Among the photographs displayed during the exhibition, the photos from the opening ceremony of the tomb of Molla Panah Vagif, one of the classics of Azerbaijani literature, and the jubilee events of literary figures were of particular interest. These exhibitions are considered a clear manifestation of Heydar Aliyev's deep concern for culture and literature [9, p. 248; 11, p. 1271].

In addition, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation plays an active role in the development of international cultural relations. For example, the Pushkin Library Project, dedicated to the memory of the classic of Russian literature Alexander Pushkin, is an example of the foundation's approach to literary heritage on an international scale. Through this project, a cultural bridge has been created between Azerbaijani and world literature, creating conditions for deepening mutual understanding and cultural dialogue [6, pp. 71–74].

Thus, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation acts as a strategic center that carries out multifaceted activities in the protection, promotion and international recognition of Azerbaijani literature and culture in general. The projects it implements are an integral part of the cultural development model of modern Azerbaijani society, both in terms of strengthening national identity and developing cultural diplomacy [7, pp. 189–190; 15, p. 23].

• Heydar Aliyev Foundation and Literary Cooperation Projects

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation has implemented a number of cultural and intellectual cooperation initiatives to promote Azerbaijani literature not only within national borders but also internationally. Among these activities, the Pushkin Library Project occupies a particularly important place. The Foundation has promoted cultural exchange and intellectual development through literature by supporting the preservation and sharing of the works of Alexander Pushkin and other classic literary works [6, pp. 71–74].

The ceremony of presenting the books of the Pushkin Library Foundation to the Heydar Aliyev Foundation on February 1, 2006, was a significant event that

served to deepen cultural dialogue and mutual understanding between Azerbaijan and Russia. This event is considered not only a symbol of friendship between the two foundations, but also an embodiment of the principle of mutual respect for different cultural heritages and sharing literary values [6, p. 73]. The event highlighted the unifying power of literature in the “human language” and emphasized the importance of cultural diplomacy that transcends borders [15, p. 22–23].

One of the important steps in this direction is the project of translating the works of Mir Jalal Pashayev into Turkish. This initiative, implemented with the support of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, has been an important stage in strengthening literary and cultural ties between Azerbaijan and Turkey. Mir Jalal Pashayev, a famous writer, philologist and educator, is known as one of the main representatives of the realist school of Azerbaijani literature with his novel “The Resurrection Man” and other works [10, pp. 357–359]. The translation of his works into Turkish is of great importance not only in terms of sharing literary heritage at the international level, but also in terms of strengthening the spiritual ties of common Turkic culture [16, pp. 185–188].

As a result of these translation projects, the works of Azerbaijani writers and poets have been brought to a wide readership in Turkey, thus opening up new opportunities for interaction and exchange of ideas in the field of literary and artistic thought [10, pp. 369–371]. These initiatives of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation have become one of the effective models serving to deepen cultural diplomacy and mutual understanding between the two countries through literature [16, p. 190].

The Foundation has initiated cultural and educational projects aimed at promoting Azerbaijani literature and strengthening the country's intellectual and scientific potential. In this context, the 9th International Book Fair held in Baku in 2023, dedicated to the 100th anniversary of Heydar Aliyev, served as an important literary platform that brought together writers, publishers, and readers [22]. The aim of the event was to introduce representatives of contemporary Azerbaijani literature at the international level, discuss new publications, and promote reading culture among the general public [22].

Azerbaijan's membership in UNESCO since 1992 has allowed the country to expand its activities in the field of cultural diplomacy, especially in the field of literature [18]. The steps taken by Heydar Aliyev in the field of cooperation with UNESCO laid the foundation for future projects representing Azerbaijani literature and art on a global level [18]. In November 2008, an international discussion on Azerbaijani literature was organized at the Diaspora Research Center in the People's Republic of China, and the role of works written in Azerbaijani Turkish in the context of world literature was discussed at this event [15, pp. 23–25].

As a result of these initiatives, Azerbaijani literature has become recognized in a wider international context as an integral part of the culture of the Caucasus region and the Turkic world in general. The cooperation between the Heydar Aliyev Foundation and the Paris office of UNESCO is of particular importance in this regard [23]. The vice-president of the Foundation, poet

and public figure Leyla Aliyeva, has actively participated in organizing programs promoting Azerbaijani literature among the younger generation and in developing international cultural relations [23]. Her initiatives are aimed at the intellectual development of young people through literature and strengthening their sense of national identity [9, p. 248].

Thus, through its projects in the field of literature, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation has achieved not only the preservation of cultural heritage, but also its international sharing. The Foundation's initiatives have transformed Azerbaijani literature into a means of dialogue connecting it with human values and included it in the global cultural exchange system [7, pp. 189–190; 10, p. 370].

• **Heydar Aliyev Foundation and UNESCO Cooperation: Global Promotion of Literary Heritage**

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation, in close cooperation with UNESCO, has played a strategic role in the international promotion of Azerbaijani literature and culture. Events, exhibitions and literary programs organized within the framework of this cooperation have not only demonstrated the richness and diversity of Azerbaijani literature, but also strengthened the country's position in the global cultural arena [18]. Joint initiatives led by the UNESCO Paris Office have contributed significantly to the growing recognition and positive reception of Azerbaijani literature worldwide [23].

As a result of this cooperation, the translation and dissemination of the works of Azerbaijani writers and poets has been facilitated, while platforms have been created for them to communicate directly with an international audience [23]. Such sharing of literary heritage has promoted not only cultural exchange, but also mutual understanding and spiritual closeness between peoples [15, pp. 23–25]. Projects carried out within the framework of UNESCO have created conditions for a deeper understanding and appreciation of Azerbaijani culture, history and identity at the global level.

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation has contributed to the preservation and revitalization of the national literary heritage by supporting the translation of over 1,300 examples of classical and contemporary Azerbaijani literature into Azerbaijani Turkish. [24] This initiative is of great importance not only in terms of archiving cultural heritage, but also in terms of transmitting literature to future generations.

In addition to translation projects supported by the Foundation, international literary festivals, conferences, and exhibitions have also played an important role in the global presentation of Azerbaijani literature [16, pp. 192–194]. Within the framework of these events, Azerbaijani authors, scholars, and artists have participated in literary gatherings held worldwide and presented the country's literary and cultural potential.

In particular, the international jubilee event organized on September 12, 2012, on the occasion of the 870th anniversary of Nizami Ganjavi, is a vivid example of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation's activity in the field of cultural diplomacy. Nizami is one of the rare figures who combined the concepts of humanity and art with universal values in his works, and the celebration

of his jubilee at the international level increased the prestige of Azerbaijani literature [7, pp. 186–189]. The aim of the event was to emphasize the importance of Nizami's legacy not only for Azerbaijan, but also in the system of universal values.

The performance "Hamse" based on the works of Nizami Ganjavi was also presented at this event. This project, prepared under the leadership of the Foundation's President Mehriban Aliyeva, consisted of five selected poems that emphasize the poetic tradition and aesthetic depth of Azerbaijani literature [5, pp. 67–69]. The performance demonstrated the unity of poetry and visual art, giving the audience a new artistic perspective on love, spirituality, and human experiences. A special place was also given to the works of the prominent poet Ismayil bey Nagam, who continued the tradition of writing "Hamse" [5, p. 68]. His poetic language is distinguished by its spiritual and philosophical line, expressing the deep layers of the human soul, the mystery of the universe, and the eternal search for perfection.

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation also played an important role in organizing an international conference dedicated to the 900th anniversary of Mahsati Ganjavi, together with the Azerbaijani Embassy in France [25]. The event, in addition to emphasizing the place of the phenomenon of Mahsati Ganjavi in the historical development of Azerbaijani culture and women's literature, also contributed to the strengthening of Azerbaijani-French cultural relations. The conference was held at the University of Haute-Alsace of the French Republic and drew the attention of the international scientific community to Azerbaijani literature [25]. This was an important step towards the systematic promotion of the country's cultural heritage in the European academic environment.

One of the most important projects of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation is the collection of publications "The Cultural Heritage of Karabakh". This five-volume series systematically documents the contributions of Karabakh to human culture in such fields as literature, music, architecture, carpet weaving and fine arts [17]. In particular, the volume "Literature" covers the role of folk art, epics and classical poetry in the formation of the literary environment of Karabakh [17]. This publication constitutes the intellectual support for the process of revitalization and reconstruction of cultural heritage in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan.

• **Heydar Aliyev Foundation and Music**

On February 2, 2005, a strategically important project in the field of culture was launched at the initiative of the Foundation President Mehriban Aliyeva; this initiative, in particular, gave a strong impetus to the formation of the country's musical landscape, prioritizing the systematic support of the national mugham tradition [2, pp. 140–144]. Aliyeva's deep appreciation for art and her consistent work in preserving and promoting Azerbaijan's cultural heritage, while promoting a vibrant cultural environment at home, also highlighted the importance of cultural diplomacy as a tool [16, pp. 190–192].

With the initiative and organizational support of the Foundation, the "Mugham Alemi" International Festival was first held in Baku in March 2009; in the

period 2011–2015, the festival continued with concerts, an international mugham competition, and scientific symposiums in Baku and the regions, bringing together world-renowned performers and researchers [2, pp. 142–145]. This platform, in addition to demonstrating the diversity of Azerbaijani music, provided support for intercultural dialogue and strengthened the presentation of national heritage on the modern stage [13, pp. 512–516].

The foundation also provides targeted support for music education: it enables the professional development of young talents through scholarship programs, master classes, and music workshops, expands access to quality learning resources, and forms a mentoring environment [16, pp. 191–192; 4, pp. 114–118]. This approach serves not only the development of individual talents, but also the sustainability of the country's music ecosystem by forming a new generation of artists [2, pp. 145–146].

The Foundation also takes a consistent line towards the preservation and promotion of musical heritage: projects are being implemented to document the ancient professional musical genre such as mugham, to archive its performance traditions and to present them to the public [2, pp. 139–143; 13, pp. 514–517]. Within this framework, concerts, exhibitions and thematic cultural events are organized, thereby increasing public awareness and artistic appreciation of Azerbaijani musical traditions [2, pp. 144–146].

Dmitri Shostakovich and **Bulbul**, the high-level celebration of the anniversaries of iconic figures of world and national musical culture in Baku in 2005–2006 is also one of the memorable projects curated by the Foundation. Concerts, exhibitions, master classes, and various cultural performances not only expressed respect for the heritage of these artists, but also demonstrated the unifying power of music that transcends borders and generations [2, pp. 143–145; 9, pp. 244–248].

Eurovision 2012 The holding of large-scale events such as the “Azerbaijani Music Night” in Baku significantly contributed to the presentation of Azerbaijan's cultural image and tourism potential to a global audience; the Foundation's organizational and communication support increased the effectiveness of these events in terms of cultural diplomacy [4, pp. 116–118; 16, pp. 192–194]. Subsequently, international presentations such as the “Azerbaijani Music Night” increased the visibility of the national musical heritage in the European cultural space and expanded interaction with diverse audiences [2, pp. 145–146].

Overall, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation's music policy – based on the pillars of education (scholarships, master classes), heritage preservation (archiving, publishing, presentation), and international promotion (festivals, concert tours) – deepens intercultural dialogue and promotes the continued recognition of Azerbaijani music at home and abroad [2, pp. 139–146; 13, pp. 512–518; 16, pp. 190–194].

Conclusion

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation, with its belief in the unifying power of culture, literature and music, plays the role of a cultural ambassador that promotes Azerbaijan not only in the region but also throughout

the world. It preserves national memory through literature, conveys a message of peace and harmony through music, and builds bridges between peoples through cultural diplomacy. The projects implemented under the far-sighted leadership of Mehriban Aliyeva have introduced the rich heritage of Azerbaijan to the modern world, and at the same time established a system that keeps this heritage alive for future generations. In this regard, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation is not only a charitable organization, but also the spiritual breath of Azerbaijan, the modern revival of national memory and a window to the world. The Foundation's activities show that art and culture are not only aesthetic values, but also the fundamental pillars of statehood, national identity and international dialogue. By protecting and sharing these values, the Heydar Aliyev Foundation makes Azerbaijan sound like a brilliant symphony on the world cultural map.

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